

Sun-Protective Behaviors in Patients with Melasma

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Background

Melasma is an acquired, chronic disorder, characterized by hyperpigmentation in sun-exposed areas of the skin

- Sun exposure is the greatest triggering and exacerbating factor in melasma
- Little is known about how patients with melasma understand and practice sun-protective behaviors such as avoiding sun exposure, seeking shade, choosing appropriate sunscreen, and using sunscreen correctly

Purpose

- Gain perspective about barriers to sun-protective behaviors of patients with melasma and to develop evidence- and data-based practice recommendations for patient education

Methods

- Mixed-methods study
 - Setting: private medical office in Orange County, CA
 - Sample: Patients ≥ 18 years of age with a melasma diagnosis
- Quantitative Data
 - Demographic questionnaire
 - Self-reported sun-protective behaviors assessed through the Sun-Exposure and Protection Index (SEPI) survey (n=21)
 - Part I: Sun-protective behaviors
 - Part II: Readiness to change
- Qualitative Data
 - Semi-structured interviews conducted to better understand the experience of having melasma and practicing sun-protective behaviors (n=13)

Conceptual Frameworks

Results

Theme: Living with Melasma
Living with melasma explored of how melasma started and what made it worse. Participants detailed feelings of guilt and regret about previous sun-exposures.

Mine is from sun exposure, I can guarantee that 100%. You know so now that's the issue...I did permanent damage to myself. I understand that. Not happy with myself about it, but it is what it is...I did things wrong a long time ago, but now the problem is that it's irreversible and it's now here and I've got to deal with it.

Sub-Theme: Sun-Protective Behaviors
Sun-protective behaviors were: wearing hats and sunglasses, using umbrellas, avoiding sun during peak hours, and wearing sunscreen. Applying and reapplying sunscreen was a challenge for participants.

I don't remember to reapply. How do you do that with makeup on? That is still challenging for me. Like with foundation and blush, I don't see how people do that.

Sub-Theme: Managing Melasma
Melasma was managed by applying prescription creams, receiving laser treatments, using sun-protection, and wearing make-up to hide the pigmentation. Feelings of insecurity (about how they looked) and frustration (about cost of treatments) were explored.

I think for me it's more of a burden than anything else just because I have never really, until I had kids, had much of a skin issue. I've never really had to wear makeup, I felt, and so now it's something I feel like I have to cover up because it doesn't look nice. Yeah, it's just been a burden for me. It's something that's made me self-conscious where I haven't had to be self-conscious before.

Discussion

- Majority of participants had low SEPI Part I and II scores- indicating increased engagement in sun-protective behaviors and increased readiness to engage in sun-protective behaviors
- Despite this, only 24% of participants reapplied sunscreen every 2 hours as recommended
- Barriers to sun-protective behaviors revealed through interviews:
 - Lack of knowledge: Participants were ignorant to the sun's damaging effects for melasma in past
 - Lack of perceived risk: Participants had excessive incidental sun exposures (not recognizing sun exposure anytime they were outside, next to an open window, or when driving)
 - Inconsistent sunscreen use: Participants reported forgetting to reapply, feeling it was inconvenient or too expensive to reapply, and not wanting to reapply over makeup

Implications for Practice

- Providers must do a better job of assessing understanding of:
 - proper application/reapplication of sunscreen
 - incidental sun exposure
- Assessment of understanding and education regarding sun protection must be ongoing
- Providers must address the economic impact of melasma to provide focused recommendations
- Providers can use the HPM to directly impact the patient's commitment to and engagement in sun-protective behaviors
- Providers can use the TTM to determine the patient's TTM stage and design interventions to motivate the individual to transition from one stage to another, or to maintain a current stage

Limitations

- Small sample size of all female and mainly Caucasian, young adult participants may be difficult to generalize to other populations
- Sample restricted to patients in Orange County, California, which may not be representative of other patients
- Statistically significant results are limited by the small sample size

Implications for Future Research

- Melasma disproportionately affects women with darker skin phenotypes, future research should include a more diverse population sample
- Melasma also occurs in male populations and it would be important to investigate how male patients protect themselves from the sun
- Additional studies should evaluate how patients choose, apply, and reapply sunscreens and how patients perceive their sun exposure risk

